

Supporting Information

Strain-Engineered Ir Shell Enhances Activity and Stability of Ir-Ru Catalysts for Water Electrolysis: An Operando Wide-Angle X-Ray Scattering Study

Tomáš Hrbek, Peter Kůš*, Jakub Drnec, Marta Mirolo, Hridya Nedumkulam, Isaac Martens, Jaroslava Nováková, Tomáš Skála, Iva Matolínová

T. Hrbek, P. Kůš, H. Nedumkulam, J. Nováková, T. Skála, I. Matolínová

Charles University, Faculty of Mathematics and Physics, Department of Surface and Plasma Science, V Holešovičkách 2, Prague 180 00, Czech Republic

E-mail: peter.kus@mff.cuni.cz

J. Drnec, M. Mirolo, I. Martens

ESRF – The European Synchrotron, ID 31 Beamline, 71 Avenue des Martyrs, Grenoble 38043, France

Results and discussion

Sample	Ir 100	Ir-Ru 50:50	Ir-Ru 25:75
Procedure step	Rate (mV h ⁻¹)	Rate (mV h ⁻¹)	Rate (mV h ⁻¹)
100 mA cm ⁻²	-31.17	99.16	129.99
200 mA cm ⁻²	75.23	105.31	84.83
300 mA cm ⁻²	139.91	103.30	85.76
400 mA cm ⁻²	133.38	96.78	80.51
500 mA cm ⁻²	246.67	96.25	99.80
600 mA cm ⁻²	186.24	107.42	109.92
300 mA cm ⁻²	59.00	38.25	46.12

Table S1: The degradation rates calculated from data in Figure 1. Each rate is taken as an average of 20 points, from minute 3 to the end of each galvanostatic step. The initial 3 minutes are omitted to avoid the region of rapid changes associated with the transition effects at the beginning of each step.

Figure S1: Uncorrected electrochemical performance. The top graph from the top shows the voltage evolution under the set current density shown in the bottom graph in galvanostatic mode.

Figure S2: The values of Ohmic resistances obtained at different parts of the primary procedure (100, 200 ... 600 mA cm⁻²) at various voltages (1.44 V, 1.48 V, 1.52 V, 1.56 V, 1.6 V). The general trend is that the Ohmic resistance decreases with voltage, as typical for the systems on sputter-etched membranes.

Analysis of electrochemical performance, the effect of temperature and pseudo-capacitance

Firstly, we take into consideration the effect of temperature. In Figure 1, we see that the Ir-Ru 25:75 catalyst operates at a slightly lower temperature throughout the procedure; however, the actual temperature difference is only 2-3 °C, which should not cause significant differences in performance. The differences are caused by the small leaks from the tubing, which lead to different heating levels. Secondly, we can utilize the remaining circuit elements from the PEIS fitting (Figure S3, charge transfer resistance R_a and pseudo capacitance CPE_a) to better understand the system and to deconvolute the origin of the various cell voltage increments. From the exponential decrement of anodic charge transfer resistances with Ohmic corrected voltage, we calculate the Tafel slopes (Figure S3) ¹¹. The Tafel slope is inversely proportional to the speed of reaction kinetics ²; for MEA Ir 100, we get values around 90 mV dec⁻¹, while for both Ir-Ru 50:50 and Ir-Ru 25:75, it is roughly 70 mV dec⁻¹. Those values are a bit higher than the values observed in the past in real single-cell (83 mV dec⁻¹ for Ir 100 and 57 mV dec⁻¹ for Ir-Ru 25:75 ³); however, not by a significant margin; it is likely caused by a lower temperature (50 °C instead of 80 °C). The exchange current densities were omitted from the analysis as they are unreliable activity metrics in single-cell systems ⁴. This is mainly due to potential interference from non-OER currents through the membrane, which can result in artificially high exchange current densities, and because of the definitory problems. Lastly, the fitted values of the double-layer pseudo capacitance CPE_a (Q_a and a_a) are used to calculate the real capacitance (Formula S1) ⁵. The values of real capacitance are in Figure S5. The double-layer capacitance is inherently differential ¹. Thus, it changes (here decreases) with growing PEIS voltage – which is separately plotted in Figure S6 for the first step of the electrochemical procedure at 100 mA cm⁻². The capacitance for the MEA Ir 100 is overall the highest (2.9 mF @ 1.52 V, 100 mA cm⁻² step), followed by MEA Ir-Ru 50:50 (2.2 mF @ 1.52 V, 100 mA cm⁻² step), while MEA Ir-Ru 25:75 demonstrated the lowest capacitance (1.8 mF @ 1.52 V, 100 mA cm⁻² step). The values are several times lower than those in our single-cell studies ³, which is caused by the lower temperature of the operation ⁶ and likely also by a worse contact of some part of the catalyst due to the construction and assembling of the *operando* cell and the lack of Pt covering layer on the Ti ³. The double-layer capacitance can be correlated to the amount of active catalyst, as the catalyst with a measurable double-layer must be in contact with PEM (definition of double-layer capacitance) and the anodic electrode; however, it does not directly correspond to the electrochemical active surface area. Therefore, if we assume that the obtained voltage is inversely proportional to the capacitance (explained separately in the next paragraph), we can normalize the electrochemical performances from Figure 1 on the capacitance. For this purpose, we used the capacitance at 1.52 V, so we are already in the region with reasonable OER currents. The goal is to compensate for the better performance (lower voltage) of the MEAs with higher double-layer capacitance, as it could be caused by the *operando-cell-related* problems, such as insufficient pressing of the catalyst, oxidation of the Ti LGDL, etc. Consequently, this may result in different rates of Ru leaching compared to the single cell and, thus, distinct morphologies, leading to different capacitances. The graph corrected on the capacitances is provided in Figure S7.

Calculation of real capacitance from pseudo capacitance

The main issue of the capacitance C as the element of an equivalent electrical circuit for PEIS is that it corresponds to an ideal electric element – an infinite, homogeneous plane flat on an atomic level ⁷. However, the surface of the electrode in our system (and any other real-life catalyst) does not even remotely resemble this. Consequently, the pure capacitance C is replaced by the pseudo capacitance CPE ,

which reflects those effects. Therefore, the EIS spectra fitting is much more precise, but in exchange, the resulting fit parameters (Q , α) do not have a direct physical meaning. However, in the case of CPE in our case, we can use the formula ⁵

$$C = \frac{1}{Q(\omega_m)^{1-\alpha}}, \quad (S1)$$

to calculate the corresponding real capacitance C of the electrochemical double layer between the ionomer (PEM) and the catalyst. Here, Q and α are the fitting parameters, and ω_m is the circular frequency corresponding to the maximal absolute value of the imaginary part of the total impedance, i.e., the top part of the typical RC EIS semicircle.

Normalization on the double-layer capacitance

Double-layer capacitance in PEM-WE corresponds to the capacitance caused by the interaction between the electrolyte (PEM) and the catalyst. It does not directly compare to the electrochemical active surface area ⁸; however, in PEM-WE, it is correlated to it as the triple-phase boundary must be present on the catalyst (ion conductivity, electron conductivity, and reactants). Therefore, we use the metrics of double-layer capacitance to show how large a portion of the catalyst (relative to other MEAs) is active in the reaction and that the capacitance is proportional to the current at a specific voltage. Since we are working in the galvanostatic mode, we need to compare the voltages, not currents. To do that, we must assume that the current I is a linear function of the cell voltage U . This is not the case in general; however, we can use the linear approximation since the $I(U)$ dependence is always monotonous and all the tested MEAs operate on a roughly similar voltage. This allows us to compare the performances of all tested MEAs (Ir 100, Ir-Ru 50:50, and Ir-Ru 25:75) without the effect of different capacitances.

Figure S3: OER Tafel slope evolution over the electrochemical procedure obtained from fitting the exponential voltage dependence of the anodic charge transfer resistance (slope).

Figure S4: OER Tafel slope evolution over the electrochemical procedure obtained from fitting the exponential voltage dependence of the anodic charge transfer resistance (slope), normalized on the initial Ir atomic loading.

Figure S5: The evolution of the double-layer capacitances during the procedure (100 mA cm^{-2} ..., 600 mA cm^{-2}) and with voltage at which the PEIS was measured (1.44 V, ..., 1.6 V). NOTE: Some points are missing if the PEIS failed to measure correctly.

Figure S6: Voltage dependence of the double-layer capacitance at the beginning of the electrochemical procedure.

Figure S7: The electrochemical voltage corrected on the double-layer capacitance. The values of capacitance at 1.52 V were used. The final values serve for relative comparison of the measured samples without the effect of the different level electrical connection.

Ex-situ XPS, EDX and TEM analyses

Figure S8: The SEM image of the sputter-etched anode of a) Ir 100, b) Ru 100, c) Ir-Ru 50:50, d) Ir-Ru 25:75 as prepared.

Figure S9: The TEM image of the sputter-etched anode of a) Ir 100, b) Ru 100, c) Ir-Ru 50:50, d) Ir-Ru 25:75 as prepared.

Figure S10: EDX obtained in TEM from Ir-Ru 25:75. Ir is blue, Ru is red/dark red. a) EDX map from one fiber b) line scan of the same image, with the intensity profile around the line.

Figure S11: Ir 4f XPS spectra measured at BOL with labeled and fitted states of Ir.

Figure S12: Ru 3d XPS spectra measured BOL with labeled and fitted states of Ru.

Oxide content	Ir	Ru
Ir 100	0.17	none
Ir-Ru 50:50	0.18	0.18
Ir-Ru 25:75	0.17	0.22
Ru 100	none	0.23

Table S2: The amount of oxide in the BOL samples measured by XPS.

State	E_B / eV	reference
Ir metallic	60.75	9
IrO ₂	61.7	9
IrO ₂ sat 1	62.8	9
IrO ₂ sat 2	67.8	9
Ir(OH) _x (3 ⁺)	62.3	9
Ir(OH) _x sat 1	62.3	9
Ru metallic	280	10
RuO ₂	280.7	10
RuO ₂ satellite	282.5	10
Ru(OH) _x	281.4	11
RuO ₃	282.2	11
RuO ₄	283.8	11

Table S3: The used states for XPS fitting with reference binding energies.

Figure S13: Ru 3d SRPES spectra of bimetallic samples measured before (B) and after (A) ex-situ electrochemistry on a model system of Ir-Ru on an Au disk for a Rotating Disk Electrode, clean samples. Measurements are done at different X-ray photon energies: 380 eV (SD: 1.3 nm) and 650 eV (SD: 2.3 nm).

Figure S14: Ru 3d SRPES spectra of bimetallic samples measured before (B) and after (A) ex-situ electrochemistry on a model system of Ir-Ru on an Au disk for a Rotating Disk Electrode, dirty samples. Measurements are done at different X-ray photon energies: 380 eV (SD: 1.3 nm) and 650 eV (SD: 2.3 nm).

Figure S15: An example of the difference between the clean and dirty samples on a S 2p spectrum for Ir-Ru 50:50.

Figure S16: Ir 4f SRPES spectra of the bimetallic samples measured after ex-situ electrochemistry on a model system of Ir-Ru on an Au disk for a Rotating Disk Electrode. Measurements are done at different X-ray photon energies of 180 eV (SD: 1.3 nm), 380 eV (SD: 2 nm), and 650 eV (SD: 3 nm).

State content	Ir ^{III} B	Ir ^{III} A	Ir ^{IV} B	Ir ^{IV} A	IrO _x B	IrO _x A
Ir-Ru 25:75						
180 eV	0.03	0.17	0.25	0.71	0.28	0.88
Ir-Ru 25:75						
380 eV	0.00	0.16	0.19	0.53	0.20	0.69
Ir-Ru 25:75						
650 eV	0.00	0.14	0.15	0.36	0.15	0.51
Ir-Ru 50:50						
180 eV	0.00	0.30	0.24	0.56	0.24	0.87
Ir-Ru 50:50						
380 eV	0.00	0.20	0.20	0.55	0.20	0.75
Ir-Ru 50:50						
650 eV	0.00	0.19	0.18	0.50	0.18	0.69

Table S4: The quantified content of different Ir oxidation states in a model system of Ir-Ru on an Au disk for a Rotating Disk Electrode before (B) and after (A) the electrochemical procedure.

Figure S17: The content of metallic Ir as a function of the SD after ex-situ electrochemistry on a model system of Ir-Ru on an Au disk for a Rotating Disk Electrode.

Figure S18: Ir-Ru 25:75 STEM analysis. a) STEM image of a particle from Ir-Ru 25:75 with a marked region for b) STEM EDX line scan with the plotted c) Ru (green) and d) Ir (red) intensity. On e) there is the corresponding EDX spectrum.

Figure S19: Ir 4f SRPES spectra of the bimetallic samples measured after ex-situ electrochemistry on a model system of Ir-Ru on an Au disk for a Rotating Disk Electrode, compared with Ir 4f XPS spectra from the sputter-etched membrane at Figure 3 of the main text. Measurements are done at different X-ray photon energies of 180 eV (SD: 1.3 nm), 380 eV (SD: 2 nm), and 650 eV (SD: 3 nm) and XPS 1486.7 eV (SD: 5.3 nm).

Sample	Ir ^{III} B	Ir ^{III} A	Ir ^{IV} B	Ir ^{IV} A	IrO _x B	IrO _x A
Ir-Ru 25:75						
XPS	0.01	0.08	0.16	0.34	0.17	0.42
Ir-Ru 50:50						
XPS	0.00	0.16	0.19	0.43	0.19	0.59
Ir 100 XPS	0.00	0.25	0.17	0.43	0.17	0.67

Table S5: The quantified content of different Ir oxidation states in operando Ir-Ru samples, measured by XPS before (B) and after (A) the electrochemical procedure.

Figure S20: The detail of the diffractogram from the tested MEAs at BOL in the operando cell with marked theoretical diffraction lines for Ir (dark blue), Ru (dark red), and Pt (dark green).

Vegard's law approximation calculation

The elemental concentration of the sample with iridium concentration x_{Ir} and measured lattice parameter a was calculated using the values a_{Ir} and a_{Ru} of the pure fcc Ir and pure fcc Ru using the linear approximation of the Vegard's law

$$x_{Ir} = \frac{a_{Ru} - a}{a_{Ru} - a_{Ir}}, \quad (S2)$$

Where the lattice parameter of the pure Ir 100 sample was used as a_{Ir} base lattice parameter. This approach is impossible for Ru as the pure Ru 100 sample contains no fcc phase. Consequently, the value a_{Ru} was extrapolated using the slope between the tabulated lattice parameter a_{Ir} and calculated lattice parameter a_{Ru} ($\text{slope}_{fcc} = (3.8394 - 3.8312) / 1 \text{ \AA} = 0.0082 \text{ \AA}$). Using this slope, the hypothetical value of a_{Ru} in our system was estimated ($a_{Ru} = a_{Ir} - 1 * \text{slope}_{fcc} = 3.842 \text{ \AA}$). This approach is necessary as the values of lattice parameters are generally upshifted compared to the theoretical values because of heat, strain, originating from the magnetron sputtering process, as discussed in the main text. Formula S2 was also used for the c lattice parameter of the hcp phase, where a was switched for c , and the used slope was $\text{slope}_{hcp} = (4.4038 - 4.2817) / 1 \text{ \AA} = 0.1221 \text{ \AA}$.

Figure S21: The comparison of the lattice parameters evolution at the first scan in the WAXS operando cell and BOL ex-situ samples.

Figure S22: The comparison of the phase content at the first scan of the operando cell and BOL ex-situ samples. Atomic concentrations were obtained from EDX.

Figure S23: The ratio of hcp phase to fcc phase without the Pt phase.

Structural evolution, details, crystallite size evolution

The obtained crystallite size at the BOL for the fcc phase are in Figure S24. The size are 5.5 nm, 5.5 nm, and 6.2 nm for Ir 100, Ir-Ru 50:50, and Ir-Ru 25:75, while for the hcp phase (Figure S24) are 7.1 nm, 6.2 nm, and 11 nm for Ir-Ru 50:50, 100, Ir-Ru 25:75, and Ru 100. Interestingly, the crystallite size of fcc and hcp phase for Ir-Ru 25:75 is the same, while for Ir-Ru 50:50 it is different, which is another sign of principally different interaction between Ir and Ru in both samples. During the electrochemical procedure, the crystallite size of fcc Ir-Ru 50:50 abruptly decreases after applying the potential. Then, it increases with time while the hcp crystallites are steadily growing, thus suggesting the presence of

Ostwald's ripening degradation mechanism ¹². On the other hand, the crystallite size of Ir-Ru 25:75 is stable.

Figure S24: The evolution of lattice parameter a , crystallite size, and phase content for the fcc phase. They were measured at the middle land, with applied potential. The states at BOL without potential are plotted as separated scatter points.

Figure S25: The evolution of lattice parameters a and c , crystallite size, and phase content for the hcp phase. They were measured at the middle land, with applied potential. The states at BOL without the potential are plotted as separated scatter points.

Homogeneity of the samples; edge-land to middle-land comparison

The comparison between the middle land and edge land measurements with applied potential is shown in Figure S26. The crystallite size and hcp lattice parameter a are omitted as they are irrelevant to our analysis or change only slightly. Firstly, we can use Figure S26 to assess the possible radiation damage, which is always a significant concern in *operando* experiments¹³. The edge land spot was exposed only to two-fifths of the radiational dose compared to the middle land spot. Yet we see no particular differences in trends between the two, which we could have attributed to the radiational damage (consistently different speed/character of changes for the middle land compared to the edge land). The most significant

difference between the middle land and edge land is visible for Ir-Ru 25:75, where the amount of both Ir fcc and hcp phases are significantly higher than in the edge land case. That means the relative amount of the Pt fcc phase is correspondingly higher; therefore, the membrane was assumably bent at the edge of the land and pushed into the channel, leading to the higher signal from the Pt, which is on the other side of the PEM. This effect is well visible only for the Ir-Ru 25:75 membrane, which fits well with our previous conclusions from the PEIS fitting, where the double layer capacitance for MEA Ir-Ru 25:75 was the lowest, suggesting specific problems in the cell assembly, and thus also electrical contact. We conclude that the measurements at the middle land are more reliable than those at the edge land.

Figure S26: The comparison of the middle land and edge land measurement when a potential is applied. Middle land measurements are always labeled with bright colors (blue, green, red), while the edge land measurements are marked with dark variants (blue, green, red).

The last scan of the WAXS data and the ex-situ measurement done on the same sample after the *operando* WAXS in transmission mode are compared in Figure S27 for completeness; however, we do not consider them reliable due to the residual Pt present on the membrane from the GDE. At the same time, the low signal from the transmission measurements on the membrane ex-situ does not allow it to fit all three phases reliably: Ir, Ru, and Pt.

Figure S27: The lattice parameter evolution of fcc and hcp phase for the ex-situ samples after and EOL scan in the operando cell. The ex-situ scans at EOL are not considered reliable due to the residual Pt on the cathode.

Figure S28: Fast Fourier Transform of the Figure 9 with a visible crystallinity of the Ir-Ru 25:75 sample at BOL

Experimental Section

Figure S29: The principal scheme of one scan in the operando WAXS PEM-WE procedure. One scan consists of 60 frames, acquired by moving the cell in the z-direction (perpendicular to the incoming X-rays).

Figure S30: The middle land and edge land positions scheme for WAXS operando PEM-WE measurements in the flow field system.

Figure S31: A Randles equivalent electrical circuit used for PEIS fitting. The effect of the cathode is omitted as negligible. R_o stands for Ohmic resistance, R_a for charge transfer resistance of the anode, and CPE_a for constant phase element of the anode.

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